

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils and soil characterization

Micronutrient status of soils and rice crop in alkali land under reclamation

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Crops grown on previously uncultivated salt-affected soils are expected to suffer from micronutrient deficiencies because of high pH and large amounts of Na^+ , HCO_3^- , and CO_3^{2-} ions. We studied the micronutrient status of surface (0-15 cm) soils and lowland rice crops in 50 alkali fields in 4 villages after 5-7 yr reclamation. Leaf blade samples (top leaves) were collected at late tillering and soil samples were taken after harvest.

The soils (Aquic/Natric Ustochreptic Camborthids) were sandy loam to loam and had pH 8.5 to 10.1, electrical conductivity 0.30 to 1.25 dS/m, 0.18-0.45% organic C, and 0-4.15% CaCO_3 .

The table presents the DTPA-extractable micronutrients in soils and the totals in rice leaves. DTPA-Zn content varied from 0.06 to 1.50 ppm. On the basis of a 0.80 ppm threshold, 60% of the soils were rated deficient in available Zn. DTPA-Fe was below the critical limit of 4.50 ppm in 14% of the samples. Available Cu (critical level 0.20 ppm) was adequate in all samples. DTPA-Mn (critical value 3 ppm) was deficient in 20% of the samples.

Leaf analysis also indicated variation in Zn content (1.2 to 23.9 ppm), 42% samples were inadequate (10 ppm Zn threshold). Fe content was inadequate (70 ppm threshold) in 30% of the samples. Mn was adequate in all samples. Cu content was inadequate (3 ppm threshold) in 92% of the leaf samples.

Both soil and plant analysis confirmed Zn deficiency in this area, but the degree of deficiency differed

considerably (see figure). While soil analysis showed 14% Fe deficiency and no Cu deficiency, leaf analysis showed that the rice crop suffered from 30% Fe and 92% Cu deficiency. Although Mn was deficient in 20% of the soil samples, leaf analysis did not show any deficiency.

These results suggest a need to redefine the critical limits of micronutrient cations for these alkali soils and for the rice crop grown on them. □

Samples (%) showing deficiency

Deficiency of micronutrients in soils and plants. Punjab, India.

Micronutrient contents of soils and plants. Punjab, India.

Micronutrient	Content (ppm)			
	Soil		Leaf blades	
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean
Zn	0.06- 1.50	0.72	1.20- 23.90	10.78
Cu	0.26- 1.34	0.82	0.17- 7.95	1.27
Fe	2.00-24.00	6.70	47.70-282.50	84.89
Mn	2.00-15.00	4.85	70.60-425.20	176.87

Effect on rice and wheat yields of adding sand and gypsum to salt-affected soils

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Salt-affected soils under the Indira Gandhi Canal Command in the Thar

desert generally are surrounded by high sand dunes. The overburden of aeolian sand due to natural conditions as well as to leveling of sand dunes by spreading them over adjoining floodplains of salt-affected soils has a special significance in the reclamation of these soils.

We used a split-plot design to evaluate the effect of sand cover (0, 5,

Table 1. Experimental soil profile (Typic Salorthid), Bikaner, India.

Depth (cm)	pH	ECe (dS/m)	Exchangeable sodium percentage	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	CaCO_3 (%)
0- 15	8.6	25.8	30.5	16.5	16.8	12.6
15- 45	8.5	22.3	35.0	16.0	23.0	11.4
45- 75	8.6	17.9	40.5	26.0	41.5	12.6
75-105	8.5	18.6	42.0	27.5	44.0	11.0
105-170	8.7	16.0	42.5	26.5	43.5	10.5

10, and 15 cm) and gypsum (0, 5, 10, and 15 t/ha) on yield of rice and wheat. Soils of the experimental field were fine-textured, salt-affected, poorly drained (infiltration rate 1.0 cm/24 h), Typic Salorthids (Table 1).

Rice variety Jhona 349 was transplanted in the wet season and wheat variety Kalyan sona was sown in the dry season. Fertilizer was 100 kg N and 18 kg P/ha.

Sand cover 5 and 10 cm thick significantly increased rice and wheat yields (Table 2). A 15-cm sand cover reduced yields, possibly because the plot was too high for efficient irrigation. Gypsum had no effect on yields.

Table 2. Yield of rice and wheat with sand cover and applied gypsum. Bikaner, India.

Gypsum (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha) with sand cover of				Mean yield (t/ha)
	0	5 cm	10 cm	15 cm	
	<i>Rice^a</i>				
0	1.8	2.8	2.7	2.1	2.4
5.0	2.2	2.7	2.8	2.3	2.5
10.0	2.2	2.6	2.5	2.3	2.4
15.0	2.3	2.9	2.5	2.1	2.5
Mean	2.0	2.8	2.6	2.2	2.5
	<i>Wheat^b</i>				
0	1.1	1.7	1.6	1.4	1.5
5.0	1.3	2.0	1.9	1.3	1.6
10.0	1.4	1.8	1.7	1.4	1.6
15.0	1.4	1.7	1.6	1.1	1.5
Mean	1.3	1.8	1.7	1.4	1.6

^aLSD = 0.33 with sand, ns with gypsum. ^bLSD = 0.50 with sand, ns with gypsum.

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Effect of *Sesbania bispinosa* decomposition time and sodicity on rice yield

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We evaluated the effect of *S. bispinosa* decomposition time (0, 1, and 2 wk under submerged conditions) at 4 levels of sodicity (exchangeable sodium percentage [ESP] 48, 36, 28, and 16) on N turnover and rice yield.

Soils were Aquic Natrustalfs (Table 1). Crops were irrigated with tubewell water (electrical conductivity 0.3 dS/m) as required.

The 1986-87 field experiment was a split-plot design with ESP levels in the main plots and decomposition period in the 40-m² subplots, with 4 replications.

Sesbania seeds were broadcast in 5 cm standing water at 70 kg seed/ha. Sowing was on 13, 20, and 27 May 1986, and 7, 14, and 21 May 1987. *Sesbania* was harvested at 50 d after seeding, chopped, and incorporated to allow decomposition periods of 0, 1, and 2 wk under submergence. Rice cultivar Jaya was transplanted 15 Jul 1986 and 9 Jul 1987. Submergence was maintained throughout rice growth. The rice crop

was fertilized with 150 kg N (urea), 9 kg Zn/ha. Half the N and all the Zn were applied at transplanting, the remaining

N was topdressed in 2 equal splits 3 and 6 wk after transplanting. Rice was harvested 30 Oct 1986 and 31 Oct 1987.

Grain yields were significantly improved at all ESP levels when *sesbania* had decomposed for 1 wk

Table 1. Initial soil characteristics. Karnal, India, 1986-87.

Soil no.	ESP	pH (1:2 soil: water)	EC (dS/m)	Exchangeable Ca + Mg (meq/100 g)	Organic C (%)	Active Mn (mg/kg)	Active Fe (mg/kg)	Available P (mg/kg)	Available K (mg/kg)
1	48	9.5	0.95	3.8	0.19	82	285	20	160
2	36	9.2	0.86	5.2	0.20	79	275	16	158
3	28	9.0	0.77	6.0	0.20	78	275	14	155
4	16	8.8	0.65	6.7	0.21	75	270	10	150

Table 2. Effect of sodicity and decomposition period of *S. bispinosa* on grain yield of rice, N contribution, and change in ESP. Karnal, India, 1986-87.

ESP	Decomposition period (wk)	Oven-dry biomass of <i>sesbania</i> (t/ha)		N turned (kg/ha)		Rice grain yield (t/ha)		ESP after rice harvest in 1987	
		1986	1987	1986	1987	1986	1987		
		48	0	3.46	3.38	94.1	93.8		5.7
	1	3.50	3.45	94.9	94.0	6.5	6.4	34	
	2	3.44	3.41	93.6	93.5	6.7	6.7	32	
36	0	3.78	3.75	102.4	100.6	6.2	6.2	26	
	1	3.85	3.85	104.3	102.2	6.7	6.7	25	
	2	3.80	3.86	103.4	101.8	6.8	6.9	25	
28	0	3.89	3.88	105.3	104.6	6.1	6.1	19	
	1	4.00	4.02	108.8	105.8	6.7	6.6	18	
	2	3.92	4.00	106.6	104.9	6.9	6.9	16	
16	0	3.90	3.95	105.7	105.9	6.2	6.2	12	
	1	3.88	3.90	105.1	106.0	6.8	6.8	10	
	2	3.99	3.98	108.1	107.5	7.0	7.0	10	
	LSD (0.05)	ESP	0.16	0.15	4.5	4.2	ns	ns	—
	Decomposition period		ns	ns	ns	ns	0.4	0.34	—